

Quantum Bound and Classical Statistical Interactions and a Constant “Energy” in Space

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Both quantum bound state equilibrium and classical statistical mechanical equilibrium are characterized by d/dt partial density $(x,t)=0$. For a quantum particle, $W(x,t)=\exp(-iEt)W(x)$ and $d(x,t)=W^*W$. Density is linked to fluid flow and arguments of pressure balance such that the overall average fluid flow is zero are made. This pressure-force balance is common in classical statistical mechanics and used to calculate the variation of density with x i.e. obtain a differential equation with $d d(x,t) /dt$ partial. A similar balance equation is used in (1) as the authors try to derive the Schrodinger equation using a fluid dynamical approach.

In this note, we try to argue that one may think of the two equilibria in terms of an energy quantity which remains constant throughout space. This energy quantity depends directly on the type of interactions in the system at any point x . For a classical ideal gas, balanced two body time reversal scattering represents the interaction. $V(x)$, a potential, does not change this fundamental manner of interacting at any given point, although it does affect density. As a result the energy related constant at each x is T , related to average kinetic energy. We argue that this already points to the dominant type of interaction creating the statistical interaction i.e. one that depends only on p in interactions which conserve kinetic energy. This “happens” to be equivalent to maximizing Shannon’s entropy, but we argue this is particular to this scenario in the sense that not all interacting systems will have this equivalence. In other words, we argue that one must be careful with regards to the maximization of entropy as a fundamental rule.

In particular, we consider the single particle bound quantum state. The interaction exists between the particle and the potential $V(x)$, but one may consider a distribution of free particle momentum probabilities i.e $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. The form $\exp(ipx)$ comes from separate arguments as is discussed in the note, but the point is that there are no two body scattering reactions occurring at a given x , neither is there acceleration from on x to another (except for a vrms mathematical quantity). Nevertheless the “free particle” $\exp(ipx)$ interacts at each x with $V(x)$. As a result of this interaction, one has free particles $\exp(ipx)$ which are no longer associated with $pp/2m$, but rather with an Eave which is a constant for every p . In other words the identity of $\exp(ipx)$ is unusual because it is linked to $\exp(ipx)$ and $pp/2m$, but also to $\sum_k a(p-k1)$, $\sum_k a(p-k2)$ etc where $V(x)=\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus each x point is associated with a constant Eave and this defines the equilibrium. (It is also equivalent to conservation of energy at each x .) In such a case, one does not maximize entropy to find $a(p)$ values.

In the two cases, the common point seems to be considering the interactions at each x and finding a constant “energy” type quantity which does not vary with x . This we argue appears to define equilibrium for both the classical statistical and quantum bound states. Instead of considering density which does not change in time at each x , there is constant energy which not only does not change in time, but has a constant value at each x which seems to be an alternative rule.

Constant Density Approach to Equilibrium

A constant density approach is often used to describe equilibrium especially in classical statistical mechanics. This is described by $d/dt \text{ partial } d(x,t)=0$ in the continuity equation:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } d(x,t) + \text{grad dot } u d(x,t) = 0 \quad ((1)) \text{ where } u(x,t) \text{ is a flow field } u(x,t)=0 \text{ for equilibrium}$$

If there is no “macroscopic” flow in equilibrium, one has a balance of forces, one being $-dV/dx$ and the other being the difference in pressure at x and $x+dx$. Using the ideal gas law $P= d(x,t) RT$ which already indicates that T is constant, an indication of equilibrium, leads to:

$$d(x,t) (-dV/dx) - P(x+dx) + P(x) = 0 \text{ or } d (-dV/dx) - RT d/dx d = 0 \quad ((2))$$

This yields a differential equation which may be solved for density i.e. $V= C \exp(-V/T)$. Again one may see that even in the case of a potential, a constant energy type quantity, namely T temperature, governs the equilibrium form. From ((2)) it is not immediately obvious that T is linked to average kinetic energy.

Interestingly a force-balance type approach may be applied to quantum bound states. In (1) the Schrodinger equation is derived using a fluid dynamical approach. The continuity equation with $u(x,t)=0$ is again used and a balance of forces is imposed i.e. $-dV/dx$ appears and is balanced by a fluid stress potential W_f such that $-dV/dx = dW_f/dx$. Integrating one obtains:

$$V + W_f = \text{Constant} \quad ((3)) \text{ which is a conservation of energy equation}$$

W_f is the average kinetic energy at x , but its form has to be established in terms of $d(x,t)$.

Classical Statistical Mechanics and Constant T

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is: $C \exp(-.5m\bar{v}^2/T - V(x)/T) \quad ((4))$
In other words there is a constant energy type parameter T which is constant at each x and we argue that this defines the equilibrium. In this case T is related to average kinetic energy. In order to determine what energy parameter is relevant we argue one must consider the interactions at a given x . For an ideal gas, there is two body scattering and we argue that a balance of an elastic reaction and its time reversed form govern the equilibrium situation i.e.

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((5))$$

Taking \ln of the second equation and linking to the first yields the MB distribution in the absence of $V(x)$.

In such a scenario no concept of entropy or its maximization is needed although this approach may be used as an alternative solution. We argue that maximization of entropy “happens” to fit this interaction scenario and is not necessarily a fundamental rule. In other words alternative

interaction schemes may not lead to maximization of entropy with constraints. In particular we consider the single particle quantum bound state.

Single Particle Quantum Bound State and Constant Eave

For a single particle quantum bound state, we assume that one has a statistical scenario. Unlike the classical statistical case, the momentum probabilities and their weights are not completely determined by the nature of the interaction. In particular we consider a free particle and argue that:

$$d/dx \text{ partial } A(x,t) = p \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt \text{ partial } A(x,t) = -E \quad \text{with} \quad A = -Et + px \quad ((6))$$

should be modified into an eigenvalue equation expressing probabilities. This leads to complex probabilities i.e.

$$-id/dx \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad \text{and} \quad id/dt \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((7))$$

The free particle probability is $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ ((8)), but one may create a distribution in order to deal with a system with a potential. In other words:

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad \text{where} \quad W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((9))$$

This leads to an average kinetic energy: $\{ \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x)$ ((10)), but this depends on x and so does not characterize the equilibrium unlike in the classical case.

One might suggest conservation of energy at each x in order to create the equilibrium situation. In general one would not necessarily assume conservation of energy at each x as necessarily required. For example, density is not constant at each x . Classically kinetic energy plus potential energy is constant at each x and this statistical system mimics at an rms level the classical situation so one might suggest conservation of energy at each x as a possible solution.

We argue that there seems to be a principle of a constant energy related parameter which is constant in x in an equilibrium situation. For the quantum bound case, the free particle $\exp(ipx)$'s interact with $V(x)$. One would at first expect an average of $p^2/2m$ to be a relevant quantity, but as argued above it is x dependent. It seems something unusual happens at each x in the quantum case. A free particle with momentum p may be described by $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ or $V_{k1} a(p-k1) \exp(ipx)$ or $V_{k2} a(p-k2) \exp(ipx)$ etc where $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus there is an issue with the identity of an $\exp(ipx)$ state. The V_k values are related to potential energy and so even in the case of a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ it cannot be $p^2/2m$ which is relevant. In fact, it must be some combination of kinetic and potential energies. If one has an equilibrium one may suggest that this combination is constant at each x just as T temperature is in the classical statistical case. To see this more clearly, assume the form of conservation of energy at each x i.e. the time-dependent Schrodinger equation:

$$\frac{1}{2m} \left\{ \sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) p p/2m \exp(ipx) \right\} + V(x) \sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) \exp(ipx) = E_n \sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((11))$$

Write $V(x) = \sum_{\text{over } k} V_k \exp(ikx)$ and collect coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ i.e.

$$p p/2m a(p) + \sum_{\text{over } k} V_k a(p-k) = a(p) E_n \quad ((12))$$

This suggests that there is a constant E_n for any p and that it holds at all x i.e. there is a spatial equilibrium, but more is occurring as there is also a kind of energy cycling equilibrium as well i.e. $E_n = \text{id/dt partial } \exp(-iEnt)$. The special energy parameter is E_n and the quantum approach is not equivalent to the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to constraints (except in the case of the ground state oscillator for which $a(p) = C_1 \exp(-ppb)$ and $W(x) = C_2 \exp(-xxb^2)$).

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that equilibrium may be characterized by an energy related value which is constant throughout space. For an ideal gas this is T , temperature, while for a single particle bound quantum state it is E_n the overall average energy. The energy parameter is linked to the type of interactions which occur at a point x . For a classical gas, two body scattering determines equilibrium at a point. $V(x)$ does not affect the scattering at this one point. This leads to T (temperature) which is related to average kinetic energy for a single particle being constant. The fact that kinetic energy is pertinent is linked to the type of interaction.

For a single particle quantum state, there are no two body interactions, the interactions are with the potential at each point x . From separate arguments a free quantum particle has a probability structure of $\exp(ipx)$. If a potential $V(x)$ is present, one may consider a distribution $\sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) \exp(ipx)$. At first one might expect an average kinetic energy to describe the situation just as it does in classical statistical mechanics as one has "free" particles. The interaction, however, even at a point x is with $V(x)$. There is no acceleration in this case (except for v_{rms} which is a math construct). Thus a combination of kinetic and potential energies seems to be linked to the constant quantity. This suggests a conservation of energy at each x point i.e. the time-dependent Schrodinger equation i.e.

$$\left[\sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) p p/2m \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) + V(x) = E_n$$

Writing $V(x) = \sum_{\text{over } k} V_k \exp(ikx)$ and collecting coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$ one has:

$$p p/2m a(p) + \sum_{\text{over } k} V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p)$$

Thus the free particle $\exp(px)$ is still present, but its identity is not clear because it is represented by $a(p) p p/2m$, $V_{k1} a(p-k_1)$, $V_{k2} a(p-k_2)$ etc. Thus one does not have a real probability function. This unusual $\exp(ipx)$ contains combinations of $p p/2m$ and V_k 's such that there is a constant E_n for each p which holds for all x . This average energy E_n seems to be the energy constant characterizing equilibrium in this case and it is not linked to maximization of Shannon's entropy (except for the ground state oscillator).

Thus we suggest that examining interactions at each x and seeking an appropriate energy like parameter which is constant for all x may be an underlying idea of equilibrium which holds for both classical and quantum systems.

References.

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